

ISic0781

Funerary inscription of Aurelius Samohil

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 540

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 29.5 cm

Width 46 cm

Depth 1.6-2 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 7-19 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. Š[LW]M 'L YŠR L 'MN 'MN ŠLWM ŠMŰ L
2. ego Aurelius Samohil conparabi
3. memoriam mi et oxoris mae uxoris meae Lasi[e] Eri-
4. ne, que fatum complebit XII kal (endas) Novebr-
5. es, diae die Veneris, luna octaba, Mero-
6. baudes iterum et Saturnino con-
7. sulibus, quae vixit annos XXIII cum
8. pace. adiuro vos per victorias qui in-
9. perant, item adiuro vos per honor-
10. es patriarcarum, item adiuro vos
11. per licem quem Dominus dedit Iu-
12. deis ni quis aperiat memoriam et mi-
13. ttat corpus alienum supra ossa nostra.
14. si quis autem aperiverit, dit fisco argendi pondo
15. dece (m)

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Peace upon Israel. Amen, amen, peace. Samuel.

I, Aurelius Samohil (=Samuel), bought the memorial for myself and my wife Lassia Irene, who completed her allotted span on the 12th day before the Kalends of November (21 October), the day of Venus (Friday), in the eighth moon (Jewish month of Heshwan), when Merobaudes for the second time and Saturninus were consuls; she lived for 23 years with peace. I adjure you by the victories (of those) who rule, likewise I adjure you by the honours of the patriarchs, likewise I adjure you by the law which the lord gave the Jews: let no-one open the memorial and put the body of someone else on top of our bones; but if anyone does open it, let them give ten pounds of silver to the treasury.

Translation (it)

Pace su Israele. Amen, amen pace. Samuel.

Io, Aurelius Samohil (=Samuel), acquistai una tomba per me e mia moglie Lassia Irene, che completò il suo percorso assegnato dal Fato dodici giorni prima delle calende di novembre (=21 ottobre), giorno di Venere (=venerdì), nell'ottava luna (nel mese ebraico di Heshwan), consoli Merobaudes per la seconda volta e Saturnino (=383 d.C.); visse ventitre anni con pace. Vi scongiuro per le vittorie di coloro che governano, parimenti vi scongiuro per gli onori dei patriarchi, parimenti vi scongiuro per la legge che il signore ha dato agli ebrei: nessuno apra la tomba e metta il corpo di qualcun altro sopra le nostre ossa; ma se qualcuno dovesse aprirlo, possa egli dare al fisco il peso di dieci libbre di argento.

Commentary

This is the only Latin (and Hebrew) inscription from the Jewish community in Sicily, and it is the longest Latin text from the Jewish diaspora in this period; it also provides the earliest datable evidence for the Jewish community in Catania. The Latin is marked by phonological and syntactical errors (e.g. mi(mihi) et

osxoris (uxori)), and it is likely that Latin was chosen not because it was familiar but because it was the high status language of public documents - the inscription aims to present Aurelius as a member of the local élite. The Hebrew is very formulaic and does not prove good knowledge of the language. Lassia is a rare name found otherwise in Campania in the early Imperial period. Threats of this sort against damage to the tomb are common in pagan and Christian inscriptions also. It is notable that Aurelius appeals equally to Roman, Jewish, and divine authority for protection.

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